

Differential Refractometric and Conductometric Studies on the Charge-Transfer Interaction of Some Metal β -Diketonates with Iodine*

R. SAHAI**, V. SINGH† and REKHA VERMA††

Department of Chemistry, V. S. S. D. College, (Kanpur University), Kanpur-208 002

Manuscript received 30 December 1980, revised 8 September 1981, accepted 10 December 1981

In order to provide further evidence on the site of interaction in metal β -diketonate chelate rings, the charge-transfer interaction of $M(\text{acac})_n$ [$M = \text{Be(II), Al(III), Fe(III), Cr(III), Co(III), VO(IV), Zr(IV), Th(IV)}$], $M(\text{BA})_n$ [$M = \text{Cu(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Co(III)}$] and $M(\text{DBM})_n$ [$M = \text{Cu(II), Pd(II), Al(III)}$] with iodine have been studied in solvents of different dielectric permittivity using differential refractometric and conductometric measurements. The K_1 , α , σ and ρ in these solvents have been calculated and the role of dielectric permittivity of the solvents in the complex formation and its limitations for these techniques have been explored and discussed. These data support interaction from the π -electron pool of the pseudo-benzenoid chelate rings of metal β -diketonates.

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC¹, dielectric^{2,3} and refractometric^{4,5} studies have indicated that some metal acetylacetonates form molecular complexes with iodine by donation of electron density from the chelate rings to σ^* -orbital of iodine. But the high equilibrium constant (K_1) obtained in these cases in comparison to benzene-iodine system may create a doubt whether the donation takes place from π -electron pool of the chelate rings or n -electrons of oxygen atom of the chelate. In our dielectric^{2,3} and refractometric^{4,5} studies, solute-solvent interaction was observed and the nature of this interaction was noted to be almost the same as was found for benzene-solvent interaction. On the one hand these data strengthen the $\pi \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transition, but on the other hydrogen bonding of $\text{Th}(\text{acac})_4$ with nitrophenols through oxygen atom favours $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transition⁶. In order to provide further evidence on the site of interaction in these chelate rings, the charge-transfer interaction of some metal acetylacetonates, $M(\text{acac})_n$ [where $M = \text{Be(II), Al(III), Fe(III), Cr(III), Co(III), VO(IV), Zr(IV), Th(IV)}$], metal benzoylacetates, $M(\text{BA})_n$ [where $M = \text{Cu(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Co(III)}$] and metal dibenzoyl methanates, $M(\text{DBM})_n$ [where $M = \text{Cu(II), Pd(II), Al(III)}$] with iodine (acceptor) have been studied using differential refractometric and conductometric measurements and the role of dielectric permittivity of the solvents in these interactions and its limitations for these techniques have been explored and discussed.

Experimental and data analysis

The materials used and method of experimentation were essentially the same as reported earlier^{4,5}.

The electrical conductance of donors, acceptor and donor-acceptor complexes have been measured by Philips -PR9500 conductivity bridge and a conductivity cell having cell constant 0.982. All measurements were carried out at 50 cycles per second at 30°. Before measuring the electrical conductance, the cell constant was calibrated each day by 0.1N KCl solution. The refractive index of solutions were measured with the help of Bausch and Lomb refractometer with an accuracy of ± 0.0002 at 30°. The conductivity experiments have been performed in two ways :

- (i) In order to use equation(1) to evaluate K_1 of these complexes, the concentration of acceptor was kept constant and the concentration of donors was varied.
- (ii) By using Gutmann's method⁷ to study the charge-transfer interaction, the equimolar stock solutions of donors and acceptor in appropriate solvents were mixed keeping the total volume constant and varying the volume of donor and acceptors.

The equilibrium constant (K_1) by electrical conductance method⁸ was measured in each case employing equation (1).

$$\delta\Delta/C_B^0 = \{K_1 C_A^0 / \rho(1 + K_1 C_A^0)\} - \{K_1 \delta\Delta / (1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2\} \quad \dots (1)$$

where C_A^0 and C_B^0 are the initial concentrations of acceptor and donor, respectively and ρ is the extent of polarization. $\delta\Delta$ is the difference in electrical conductance of solution (donor+acceptor) and solvent. A plot of $\delta\Delta$ vs $\delta\Delta/C_B^0$ was linear with a

* A part of this work has been presented at Golden Jubilee Session of National Academy of Sciences, India, held at Allahabad during October 28-27, 1980.

** To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

† Present Address : Department of Biochemistry, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi.

†† Present Address : Department of Chemistry, M. K. P. Girls' Degree College, Dehradun (U.P.).

slope = $-K_1/(1+K_1C_A^0)^2$ and intercept = $K_1C_A^0/\rho(1+K_1C_D^0)$. Conductometric titration technique has indicated 1:1 stoichiometry of these complexes.

The equilibrium constant (K_1) and extent of electronic polarization (α) from differential refractometric method have been calculated by using equation (2) recently developed by Sahai *et al*⁹.

$$\frac{\Delta\Omega C_{DA}}{C_D^0} = \left\{ \frac{K_1 C_A^0 / \alpha (1 + K_1 C_A^0)}{K_1 \Delta\Omega C_{DA} / (1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2} \right\} \dots (2)$$

where the notations have their usual meanings and their values have been calculated as reported earlier⁹. As expected from equation (2), a plot of $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ vs $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}/C_D^0$ was linear (Fig. 1) with a slope = $-K_1/(1+K_1C_A^0)^2$ and intercept = $K_1C_A^0/\alpha(1+K_1C_A^0)$. Differential refractometric titration technique has also indicated 1:1 stoichiometry of these complexes.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ vs $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}/C_D^0$ for molecular complexes of some metal β -diketonates with iodine in CCl_4 at 30° .

The K_1 has also been calculated using Yoshida and Osawa's¹⁰ equation (3),

$$K_1 = 2 \sqrt{k} \left\{ \sqrt{k(C+C')} - (C+kC') \right\} / (C-kC')^2 \dots (3)$$

where C and C' are the maximum concentration of both the systems and k is the maximum deviation from the additive line when molar ratio of solutes is

plotted against square of refractive index (n^2). The K_1 has also been calculated by modified Yoshida and Osawa's method as developed by Sahai and Singh¹¹. In this method, instead a plot of n^2 vs molar ratio of solutes, $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ is plotted against molar ratio of solutes which have indicated 1:1 stoichiometry of these complexes. The stoichiometry of these complexes has also been calculated by plotting $\phi_D C_A^0$ (or $\phi_D / \Delta\phi_{DA} C_A^0$) against X_D (mole fraction of donor), the maxima occur at $X_D = n / (1+n)$. At this maxima if $n=1$, then K_1 may be calculated by equation (4) as recently developed by Sahai *et al*⁹.

$$K_1 = (\phi_D / \Delta\phi_{DA}) / (C_D^0) (1 - \phi_D / \Delta\phi_{DA})^2 \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta\phi_{DA} = \phi_{DA} - \phi_{CD}$ and $\phi_{CD} = \phi - \phi_D$. These values have been calculated as reported earlier^{9,11,15}.

Results and Discussion

The equilibrium constants (K_1) of the charge-transfer complexes of metal β -diketonates with iodine have been calculated by observing the refractive indices of solvent, acceptor, donor and solution (donor+acceptor). The refraction per cm^3 of solvent (ϕ_0), acceptor (ϕ_A), donor (ϕ_D) and solution (ϕ) were then calculated as reported earlier^{4,5,11-15}. From these data, the difference in refraction per cm^3 of solution and solvent ($\delta\phi$), solution and acceptor ($\Delta\phi_A$), solution and donor ($\Delta\phi_D$) and the refraction per cm^3 due to charge-transfer complex ($\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$) have been calculated. An appreciable increase in $\delta\phi$, $\Delta\phi_A$, $\Delta\phi_D$ and $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ values with the increase of donor concentration and keeping the acceptor concentration constant have been interpreted due to the charge-transfer from the π -orbital of pseudo-benzenoid ring of metal β -diketonates to the σ^* -orbital of iodine. This is in parallel agreement with our earlier observations^{1,4}. The best values of equilibrium constant and related parameters have been obtained when differential refractometric method has been applied. The K_1 calculated from this method applying several techniques (equations 2, 3 and 4) are recorded in Table 1. These values are quite comparable with those obtained from spectrophotometric method¹.

Gutmann *et al*^{14,15} have shown that the appearance of a peak in conductivity concentration (of D and A) plot is a clear indication of complex formation between donor(D) and acceptor(A). Since the conductivities (σ) are additive, it follows that σ in the absence of interaction should be linearly related to the concentration of the titrant. The stoichiometry of the complex may be deduced from the concentrations of D and A at the conductivity peak. A representative plot is shown in Fig 2. The value of the conductivity peak above a base line connecting the conductivities of pure donor and acceptor solution is a measure of the excess conductivity caused by the formation and subsequent dissociation of the complex. The

TABLE 1 - COMPARISON OF DIFFERENTIAL CONDUCTOMETRIC AND REFRACTOMETRIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT AND RELATED DATA* FOR 1:1 MOLECULAR COMPLEXES OF METAL β -DIKETONATES WITH IODINE AT 30° IN: 1. CCl_4 ($\epsilon=1.96$); 2. $\text{CCl}_4+\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ (3:1; $\epsilon=10.89$); 3. $\text{CCl}_4+\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ (1:1; $\epsilon=19.60$); 4. $\text{CCl}_4+\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ (1:3; $\epsilon=28.78$); 5. CH_2CN ($\epsilon=37.50$)

System/ Solvent	Conductometric data			Refractometric data				Δn_{DA} maxima	
	K_1 (l. mol ⁻¹) Eq. 1	$\sigma_p \times 10^6$	ρ	K_1 (l. mol ⁻¹)			$\kappa \times 10^4$		
	Eq. 2	Eq. 3	Eq. 4	Eq. 2	Eq. 3	Eq. 4			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
Be(acac)₂-I₂									
1.	10.32	8.0	100.00	20.00	20.72	19.33	12.41	0.60	
2.	12.30	19.0	120.00	16.00	17.25	17.46	11.20	0.58	
3.	13.40	45.0	140.45	14.00	14.55	15.12	11.12	0.52	
4.	14.20	58.0	165.55	12.04	12.20	13.24	11.02	0.50	
5.	15.70	72.0	200.00	10.62	11.46	10.46	10.86	0.45	
Al(acac)₃-I₂									
1.	110.45	8.2	160.23	174.41	179.20	183.00	0.75	0.42	
2.	130.23	40.0	171.55	165.55	172.46	180.00	0.62	0.41	
3.	140.40	120.0	180.00	145.40	162.56	172.46	0.56	0.40	
4.	151.46	220.0	185.42	135.40	145.22	158.55	0.52	0.38	
5.	160.00	330.0	200.00	120.30	140.45	150.45	0.51	0.36	
Fe(acac)₃-I₂									
1.	640.55	—	200.45	256.41	245.79	269.18	1.04	0.48	
2.	710.23	—	210.10	250.00	240.35	250.14	1.00	0.46	
3.	740.56	—	230.35	245.00	231.25	235.45	0.95	0.45	
4.	800.00	—	252.45	232.20	220.35	210.20	0.80	0.42	
5.	820.34	—	260.52	220.00	210.35	186.26	0.70	0.40	
Cr(acac)₃-I₂									
1.	890.45	12.2	340.25	833.33	842.87	892.85	1.63	0.66	
2.	910.23	80.0	360.65	820.00	810.46	865.46	1.60	0.60	
3.	940.45	210.0	390.45	800.00	742.45	810.52	1.58	0.58	
4.	960.00	340.0	400.00	740.45	720.56	800.46	1.40	0.57	
5.	1000.00	415.0	450.50	720.20	700.46	780.85	1.35	0.54	
VO(acac)₃-I₂									
1.	1410.46	13.8	400.00	952.38	918.26	897.42	2.31	0.69	
2.	1460.35	130.0	410.00	920.00	900.02	860.23	2.30	0.67	
3.	1520.23	250.0	420.40	905.00	850.46	810.45	2.20	0.62	
4.	1580.45	350.0	430.45	840.00	810.23	780.32	2.10	0.60	
5.	1620.00	440.0	435.45	780.45	760.10	710.46	2.00	0.58	
Co(acac)₃⁺-I₂									
1.	1420.35	14.2	310.45	1176.47	1063.47	1083.33	2.76	0.72	
2.	1480.75	140.0	330.20	1120.45	1020.20	1030.35	2.70	0.70	
3.	1510.50	265.0	340.45	1100.00	1000.00	960.56	2.43	0.68	
4.	1570.20	365.0	400.00	1040.45	960.65	910.35	2.35	0.67	
5.	1610.35	480.0	420.45	1000.00	920.45	840.56	2.20	0.65	
Zr(acac)₄-I₂									
1.	1440.35	15.5	375.60	1175.00	1175.91	1185.34	2.90	0.74	
2.	1520.46	180.0	385.55	1110.45	1140.56	1110.45	2.68	0.71	
3.	1560.23	370.0	400.00	1040.30	1060.23	1080.40	2.10	0.70	
4.	1580.46	490.0	410.24	1000.20	1000.00	1020.56	2.10	0.68	
5.	1610.00	520.0	420.35	940.45	940.20	980.32	2.00	0.65	
Th(acac)₄-I₂									
1.	2010.30	16.2	365.75	2120.00	2113.12	2172.49	3.25	0.91	
2.	2115.23	185.0	370.75	2080.56	2100.00	2120.56	3.00	0.90	
3.	2210.55	390.0	380.35	2040.40	2040.46	2100.00	2.85	0.86	
4.	2240.45	510.0	400.00	2000.00	2000.00	2040.56	2.75	0.82	
5.	2300.00	545.0	410.35	1940.45	1940.50	2000.00	2.60	0.80	
Cu(BA)₂-I₂									
1.	200.00	9.8	275.00	320.00	335.00	345.00	1.08	0.52	
2.	210.85	57.8	280.00	300.20	320.00	320.00	1.00	0.50	
3.	230.40	155.0	300.45	270.45	310.46	300.45	0.80	0.48	
4.	240.46	281.4	310.45	260.60	286.40	260.46	0.75	0.46	
5.	285.55	378.0	320.45	230.20	260.35	240.35	0.70	0.42	

(Table I Contd.)

	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Al(BA)₃-I₂								
1.	160.55	9.2	260.00	270.00	278.00	282.00	1.00	0.51
2.	200.25	40.0	265.42	260.55	255.23	260.46	0.90	0.50
3.	210.46	130.0	280.80	240.35	230.46	230.46	0.80	0.48
4.	240.46	270.0	290.95	220.35	220.35	200.40	0.70	0.46
5.	260.35	365.0	300.00	200.00	200.20	180.56	0.60	0.45
Cr(BA)₃-I₂								
1.	850.50	14.0	240.00	906.00	925.00	930.00	2.20	0.66
2.	900.85	145.0	245.00	900.00	900.25	910.46	1.98	0.65
3.	940.35	282.0	250.56	840.46	860.35	830.46	1.90	0.62
4.	1000.00	402.0	260.00	810.30	800.46	810.85	1.80	0.60
5.	1020.35	475.0	365.55	800.45	760.35	800.35	1.72	0.57
Co(BA)₃-I₂								
1.	1000.00	17.0	330.30	1240.00	1265.00	1180.75	3.00	0.78
2.	1040.40	142.0	340.40	1210.45	1220.46	1120.75	2.80	0.76
3.	1100.00	284.0	345.50	1180.55	1140.56	1080.56	2.65	0.72
4.	1140.45	420.0	360.80	1120.45	1090.30	1060.40	2.40	0.70
5.	1200.00	475.0	380.80	1040.60	1020.20	1000.20	2.00	0.66
Cu(DBM)₃-I₂								
1.	1260.45	14.5	330.50	1505.04	1520.00	1430.00	3.20	0.82
2.	1300.00	150.2	350.00	1450.65	1500.00	1400.23	3.00	0.80
3.	1420.75	270.0	365.23	1410.42	1460.32	1320.50	2.80	0.80
4.	1460.45	362.0	370.00	1360.55	1420.56	1300.46	2.40	0.78
5.	1500.00	472.4	380.00	1310.60	1380.50	1240.50	2.20	0.76
Pd(DBM)₃-I₂								
1.	540.23	11.8	380.55	785.94	770.00	730.00	2.85	0.62
2.	575.45	68.0	400.20	740.45	710.56	710.56	2.60	0.60
3.	600.80	202.0	410.46	710.55	700.20	700.23	2.40	0.58
4.	640.00	330.6	430.23	700.45	640.56	640.35	2.30	0.56
5.	700.00	405.0	440.00	685.20	610.23	610.23	2.10	0.54
Al(DBM)₃-I₂								
1.	850.55	14.6	310.00	—	1070.00	1040.45	—	0.70
2.	900.00	142.8	355.55	—	1000.56	990.56	—	0.68
3.	940.60	291.3	360.45	—	960.02	910.46	—	0.60
4.	1000.00	380.0	365.00	—	910.35	840.23	—	0.58
5.	1080.80	470.0	390.00	—	880.35	810.46	—	0.56

* A standard deviation of 2.0-5.0% in these values has been estimated.

Fig. 2. Plots of molar ratio of solutes vs σ in $\text{COI}_4 + \text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ (1 : 1) mixture for some $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n - \text{I}_2$ complexes indicating obscured curve of $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_3 - \text{I}_2$ system and clear curve for other systems.

complex may not be fully dissociated; from the theory it follows that the dissociation constant has to be allowed for, since the carrier concentration is proportional to the concentration of M of the reagent, rather to αM , where α is the dissociation constant of the complex. A well developed conductivity maxima indicated in Fig. 2 for $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3 - \text{I}_2$ complex is not always obtained. In case of $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_3 - \text{I}_2$ complex, a steep sloping base line caused by serious mismatch of initial conductivities of the donor and acceptor solutions tend to yield ill-defined, or completely obscured, conductivity peak (Fig. 2). The correct stoichiometry for this case has been determined by correcting the background conductivity obtained by linear interpolation by plotting $\sigma - \sigma_0$ vs relative concentration (Fig. 3). A well developed maxima at 1 : 1 stoichiometry is thus obtained. The ill defined maxima in case of $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_3 - \text{I}_2$ complex may be due to the conductivity competition of $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_3$ with Iodine. Since the conductivity of $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_3$ is high compared to other $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n$, it may create hindrance in order to get well developed maxima as has been observed in other cases. Therefore, in conductometric measurements, the correct choice of solvent is very important. If its conductivity is too high, conductance changes due to complex formation may become obscured

Fig. 3. Corrected stoichiometric plots of molar ratio of solutes vs $\sigma - \sigma_0$ indicating well developed maximum at 1 : 1 for $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_2 - \text{I}_2$ in the $\text{CCl}_4 + \text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ mixture of 3 : 1 ($\Delta - \Delta - \Delta$), 1 : 1 ($\circ - \circ - \circ$), 1 : 3 ($\bullet - \bullet - \bullet$) and CH_3CN ($\blacktriangle - \blacktriangle - \blacktriangledown$) at 30° .

and if the permittivity is too low, the complex may fail to dissociate. $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{BA})_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{DBM})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ complexes with iodine show a well developed maxima in CCl_4 but haphazard curves were noted in CHCl_3 . Through these plots we are unable to specify the stoichiometry of these complexes. This may be due to the acceptor characteristic of CHCl_3 which may compete with these donors. Recently, Sahai and Badoni¹⁶ have shown that CHCl_3 can be held through a weak hydrogen bond with π -electrons of pseudo-benzenoid ring of $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$. In these cases by titrating CHCl_3 with donors in CCl_4 a well defined maxima at 1 : 1 was obtained which indicates 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the complex. In order to specify the site of interaction in $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n - \text{CHCl}_3$, the conductometric titrations of benzene- CHCl_3 and $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n - \text{CHCl}_3$ systems have been carried out in CH_3CN . It has been observed that in $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n - \text{CHCl}_3$ complexes, the change in electrical conductance was greater than benzene- CHCl_3 systems. The σ maxima for $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n - \text{I}_2$ systems also noted to be greater than the σ maxima for benzene- CHCl_3 system. This may be due to the better donor capability of $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n$ than benzene. The presence of two CH_3 groups in these systems has made the molecule more basic than benzene. Since in both the cases of $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n - \text{I}_2$ and benzene- I_2 , the order of change in conductance is the same, the site of interaction obviously will be the same.

In order to confirm the site of interaction through refractometric studies, an equimolar solution of $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_2$ and CHCl_3 (10^{-2} l. mol⁻¹) in

* Though CCl_4 also acts as electron acceptor with several hydrocarbons^{17,18}, compared to CHCl_3 , it may be assumed to be inert.

cyclohexane were mixed, varying the volumes of donors and acceptor and keeping the total volume of the solution constant, and the refractive indices were measured. A small deviation in both the cases were noted which indicates weak interaction between donor and acceptor**. In case of $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_2 - \text{CHCl}_3$, the $\Delta\Omega_{\text{CDA}}$ maxima was noted to be at 0.20 whereas in benzene- CHCl_3 it was at 0.17. This indicates that the extent of interaction in $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_2 - \text{CHCl}_3$ is more than benzene- CHCl_3 . This may again be interpreted as due to better donor ability of $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n$ in $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n - \text{CHCl}_3$ systems because of the presence of two CH_3 groups in $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n$ as has already been described. In order to specify the site of donation in $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n - \text{CCl}_4$ interactions, the refractometric studies have already been made⁸ and it was observed that the extent of interaction is the same as was found in aromatic hydrocarbons- CCl_4 systems.

In case of $\text{M}(\text{BA})_n$ and $\text{M}(\text{DBM})_n$ systems, the doubt regarding the site of interaction becomes more as to whether the donation takes place through the π -electron pool of pseudo-benzenoid ring or through the π -electrons of the benzene ring. In these cases the donor- CHCl_3 interactions were studied in CH_3CN by conductometric and in cyclohexane by refractometric techniques. In both the studied, 1 : 1 complex was noted and $\Delta\Omega_{\text{CDA}}$ maxima have indicated the order of interaction : $\text{Al}(\text{DBM})_3 > \text{Al}(\text{BA})_3 > \text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$. The K_1 values have also indicated the same order of interaction (Table 1). This may be interpreted as due to better donor capability of $\text{M}(\text{DBM})_n$ than $\text{M}(\text{BA})_n$ and $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n$. In $\text{M}(\text{DBM})_n$ and $\text{M}(\text{BA})_n$ systems, the presence of additional π -electrons have made the molecule more basic rather than the inductive effect of $-\text{CH}_3$ or $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ groups. This observation clearly indicates that in metal β -diketonate- I_2 interactions, the site of interaction through the π -electron pool of the benzenoid ring cannot be ignored.

The conductivity at the conductivity peak (σ_p) of different charge-transfer complexes are listed in Table 1. From this table, it is evident that the value of σ_p increases with the increase in dielectric constant of the medium. Similar observation of σ_p with dielectric constant of the medium has been reported in case of *p*-phenylenediamine-picric acid complex²⁰. On the basis of this observation, it can be said that the total number of ions carrying the current at the stoichiometry of the complex increases with increase in the dielectric constant of the medium. Subsequently, the complex should ionise to a greater extent in the solvent of high dielectric constant. This is in parallel agreement with our earlier observation. From Table 1, it is also evident that as soon as the dielectric constant of the medium increases, the $\Delta\Omega_{\text{CDA}}$ maxima

** A change in electron cloud density in neutral atom or molecule will lead to a change in the polarizability. Since the complex is generally more polar than the components, the electronic polarizability or refractive index increases and the deviation depends upon the extent of interaction between donor and acceptor^{9,10,11,19}.

decreases. In refractometric measurements, the refraction per cm^3 due to the complex always depends upon the concentration of donor and acceptor. In the solution, the concentration of DA complex becomes low and the concentration of ionic species becomes high. This dissociation ($\text{DA} \rightleftharpoons \text{D}^+ + \text{A}^-$) depends upon the dielectric constant of the medium. Therefore, $\Delta\Omega_{\text{CDA}}$ maxima were found to be the least in CH_3CN than in CCl_4 or cyclohexane. This is because the dissociation of the complex in CH_3CN becomes maximum leaving the concentration of the complex least in the solution whereas the reverse was the case in CCl_4 and in cyclohexane. Thus we may infer upon the limitations of the conductometric and refractometric methods. In refractometric measurements, the solvent used should be of low permittivity because high permittivity of the solvent causes dissociation of the complex leading to the error in the determination of accurate and reliable value of K_1 . But in conductometric measurements, the solvent should be of high permittivity which could ionise the complex as $\text{DA} \rightleftharpoons \text{D}^+ + \text{A}^-$. Thus, in order to get good results through refractometric methods, the solvent should be of low permittivity, but to get good results through conductometric methods, the solvent should be of high permittivity.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from UGC to (V. S.) and from CSIR to (R. V.) is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are grateful to Professors P. R. Singh and P. C. Nigam (I. I. T., Kanpur) for providing refractometric facilities and encouragement during the progress of this work and to Professor P. P. Singh

(M.L.K. College, Balrampur, Gonda) for providing the electrical conductance measurement facilities.

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